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“THE ONE YOU LOST”

For so long, I carried the blame,
I bowed my head and owned the shame;
I thought the fault was mine to bear,
as if you had no wrong to share.

I blamed myself for every tear,
for every doubt and every fear;
I called myself the one who failed,
the coward heart that broke and paled.

But now the truth has found its view,
the greater loss belongs to you;
you let me go, you turned away,
from one who loved you every day.

It is your loss, and this is true,
no one will love you as I do;
so now I see what pain once knew,
it was not me, it has been you.